

METHODS OF INVESTIGATION OF CHRONIC LIP CRACK

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ANNOTATION

To date, numerous methods for the diagnosis and treatment of chronic lip fissures have been presented, including schemes for both general and local treatment. However, the number of patients with this pathology tends to constantly grow, so the search for new drugs and methods for its treatment is important and justified. The article presents a clinical case of local treatment of a chronic lip fissure with the inclusion of a blockade with a local anesthetic and the application of a collagen-containing preparation in the treatment regimen, which showed a good clinical result.

Key contributors: malignancy, epithelialization, lip fissure, blockade, mucosa, pathology, collagen, local, vasoconstrictor, etiopathogenesis.

Introduction

Relevance.

A total of 22 patients were examined (the study group – 11 people; the comparison group - 11 people). The clinical examination was carried out according to the generally accepted method. It consisted of a survey, an inspection. Anamnesis of life and disease was collected. Revealed the presence of transferred and concomitant diseases, bad habits, occupational hazards. In the presence of general somatic diseases, the anamnesis of a certain disease was collected, the nature and tactics of previously conducted treatment were determined. We paid attention to the allergological status and heredity.

When examining patients, we excluded clinical signs of malignancy of cracks. Bacterioscopic examination was performed in 50% of patients (11 people), which revealed the usual mixed microflora of the oral cavity. Blood examination was performed in 4 patients: general clinical analysis: bacteriological: no glucose; for HIV infection.

Discussion. All observed patients underwent bacteriological studies. Often, it is not possible to determine the cause of an infectious lesion of the oral mucosa due to the presence of a huge number of microorganisms in the oral cavity. The possibility of anaerobic infection depends on the number of anaerobes in the wound, morphological features and virulence of the pathogen, the influence of concomitant microorganisms, etc.

The realization of the pathogenic properties of anaerobes is possible with the appropriate state of the body and only in the presence of tissue areas deprived of blood supply, chronic intoxication of the body, accompanied by a decrease in protective forces, etc. his patients To choose adequate antibacterial agents for effective treatment.

Result.

Method for determining anaerobes Scrapings from cracks were sown in Kitta - Tarozzi medium incubated under anaerobic conditions at 37 ° C for 3-4 days; the bottom growth of bacteria was observed. Then they were transplanted to blood sugar agar in Petri dishes and into a column of sugar nutrient agar in a test tube. The crops were also incubated under anaerobic conditions. Delicate transparent colonies were formed on the surface of the tetanus bacillus blood agar, surrounded by an inconspicuous hemolysis zone. To obtain a pure culture, suspicious colonies were transplanted into test tubes with Endo medium and stored under a layer of vaseline oil. For the purpose of qualitative and quantitative determination of anaerobic pathogenic microflora, gas-liquid chromatography was carried out according to the method of A.I. Karpishchenko and G.I. Elkin (2001) on the basis of the Department of Microbiological Chromatography of the Laboratory, Biochemistry of TMA. Results of the gas-liquid test, the most common pathogen of HRT was mixed microflora ($54.2 \pm 1.1\%$) with a

predominance of anaerobic non-clostridial microflora, gram-negative bacteria of the genus *Bacteroides* and a lesser degree of gram-positive cocci of the genera *Peptococcus* and *Peptosreptococcus*.

Conclusion.

With the help of bacteriological studies, the determination of anaerobes was carried out. The possibility of anaerobic infection depends on the number of anaerobes in the wound, morphological features and virulence of the influence of concomitant microorganisms, etc. The realization of the pathogenic properties of anaerobes is possible with the appropriate state of the body and only in the presence of tissue areas deprived of blood supply, chronic intoxication of the body, accompanied by a decrease in its defenses, etc.

List of literature.

1. Khanov A.M. Modern system of organizational forms of active prevention of breast cancer (based on the model of the Republic of Bashkortostan): Abstract of the dissertation. ... Doctor of Medical Sciences. - Rostov-on-Don, 2001. - 50 P.
2. Tsvetkova L.A., Arutyunov S.D., Petrova L.V., Perlamutrov Yu.N. Diseases of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity and lips. - M.: MEDpress-inform. -2006.-288 p.
3. Chizhikova T.S., Kravtsova E.O. The clinical picture of the oral cavity in people living in various ecological areas of Volgograd and the Volgograd region. - Volgograd. - 2000. - pp. 132-135.
4. Shargorodsky A.G., Rutsky N.F. Benign and malignant tumors of soft tissues and bones of the face. - M.: VUNMC, 1999. - pp. 122-125.
5. Yagovdik N.Z., Kachuk M.V., Zemskova Z.A. Placenta suspension in the complex therapy of patients with eczema and diffuse neurodermatitis // Abstracts of the 6th All-Russian. Congress of Dermatologists and Venereologists. - M., 1989. - 4.2. - pp. 483-484.

6. Archard N.O. Dental diseases of internal and external nature. - New York: C. Thomas, 1996. - 590 p.

7. Bezek D.M. et al. Acute gangrenous mastitis and cheilitis associated with enterotoxin-releasing *Staphylococcus aureus* in goats // *Can. Vet. J.* - 2005. - Volume 36. - No.2. - pp. 106-107.

8. Brook R.I. Exfoliative cheilitis // *Oral surgery.* - 1988. - Vol. 45.- No. 1. - pp. 52-60.

9. Costa i Silva Ya. Fucking depression. Editorial. *WPA Educational Bulletin on Depression*, 1993;1:1.